

Automatic term extraction and scientometric analysis in information science: A few-shot learning approach

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Abstract

Information science terminology is an important component of the discipline knowledge system. Automatically extracting information science terms from the full-text of academic papers is the premise of bibliometrics analysis and associated knowledge mining from the conceptual dimension. Currently, pre-trained models usually require domain-adaptive training and fine-tuning on large-scale datasets in order to adapt to downstream tasks. We designed a generative term extraction method, combined with few-shot learning strategy and fine-tuning, to improve the text generation ability of GPT3 for the specific term extraction task. It is able to extract information science terms more accurately in the case of small-scale labeled datasets. In the comparison experiments, this method outperformed natural language understanding models such as BERT and SciBERT in term extraction. Finally, from the perspective of terminology, the research topics and directions in the field of information science were explored through scientometric and social network analysis.

Introduction

A term is a linguistic representation of a concept (Sager, Dungworth & McDonald, 1980) and is a word designation for a general concept in a particular field of expertise. As the smallest knowledge unit, information science term is the core constituent of the discipline knowledge system and is an important source that carries the research history. Through cutting-edge deep learning and pre-training technology, as well as the recognition and analysis of information science terms, we can sort out the research focus and technical evolution paths in the development history of information science, which is of great significance for promoting technological innovation and intelligence decision-making, and improving the terminology system of information science theories and methods.

Automatic Term Extraction (ATE) belongs to the category of information extraction tasks. Compared with the classic deep learning models (Pinheiro & Collobert, 2014; Terry, Hoste & Lefever, 2022), the pre-trained models can combine contextual information better to learn term features due to their powerful textual representation. Ding et al. (2021) extracted key phrases from abstracts of Chinese medical academic literature based on BERT model, and the F-score was significantly improved compared with BiLSTM-CRF. Li et al. (2021) compared text representation difference between the pre-trained models and the traditional word embedding methods. BERT and SciBERT performed better than GloVe embedding in the named entity recognition task of the ACL paper dataset. They further introduced data augmentation

techniques to improve the robustness and generalization capabilities of SciBERT on small-scale labeled datasets.

By continuing pre-training on domain texts, the pre-trained models can be made more applicable to domain-specific term extraction. Si et al. (2019) continued pre-training models such as ELMo and BERT on MIMIC-III clinical texts, and found that BERT performed best in clinical concept extraction. Yang et al. (2020) compared BERT, RoBERTa, ALBERT and ELECTRA for clinical concept extraction before and after domain-adaptive training, and found that the RoBERTa model pre-trained on clinical text had the highest F-score, which was significantly improved compared with LSTM-CRF.

From the above research, it can be found that most of the pre-trained based ATE methods use Natural Language Understanding (NLU) models (e.g., BERT), which usually outperform traditional machine learning and deep learning models. However, in the case of scarce labeled text, BERT is prone to overfitting after fine-tuning, and its performance may be weaker than that of the classic neural network models.

Currently, there is a lack of high-quality labeled terms corpus in information science discipline, which cannot provide large-scale data support for supervised machine learning. In contrast, the few-shot learning strategy can build high-performance models using small-scale labeled training sets, thus reducing manual labeling costs and computing resources. Therefore, we proposed an automatic term extraction method based on few-shot learning. By fine-tuning the GPT3 model with a small number of samples, it can extract terms from the full-text of information science academic papers through text generation. We also took the *Journal of Informetrics* as an example to analyze the information science terms through scientometric methods, and explored the research topics and hotspots from a conceptual perspective.

Method

Data source

We used the full text of SSCI indexed journals in information discipline as the data source. At this stage of the research, we only selected the papers from *Journal of Informetrics*. The papers were published from 2007-2018. After data cleaning, 838 research papers were finally obtained, containing a total of 36,973 paragraphs, 182,267 sentences, and 4,344,411 words.

Data annotation

ATE is similar to named entity recognition (NER), which is a type of supervised learning task that requires the construction of labeled datasets. However, completely manual labeling of information science terms is costly in terms of labor and difficult to ensure labeling consistency. In the case of few-shot learning, we combined dictionary matching and manual proofreading, and only labeled a small amount of data for model training and evaluation.

The Research Center for Humanities and Social Computing of Nanjing Agricultural University has constructed the Chinese Social Sciences Term Index (CSSTI), which contains bilingual terms in 22 social science disciplines. There are 1403 English terms in information science.

We randomly sampled 12,000 sentences from the *Journal of Informetrics* dataset, and identified the information science terms in the sentences by the maximum matching algorithm. After the labeling was completed, the sentences that did not match the terms were deleted, and finally 2373 sentences were retained as the labeled dataset.

Generative term extraction method based on few-shot learning

Deep learning methods usually require the construction of large-scale supervised datasets. Although the NLU models represented by BERT introduces a two-stage mode of pre-training and fine-tuning to reduce the amount of labeled data required, tens of thousands or even more data are still required for fine-tuning to adapt model parameters to downstream tasks.

The GPT3 (Brown et al., 2020) is a Natural Language Generation (NLG) model inherently suitable for left-to-right text generation tasks. It is trained on a massive amount of web text with 175 billion parameters. We can interact with the model and get generated answer in a few-shot or even zero-shot manner directly by entering the prompt to complete specific downstream tasks.

Since the pre-training corpus of GPT3 is generic text, if it is directly used for term extraction of information science domain papers, it may introduce noise while generating terms, regardless of zero-shot, one-shot, or few-shot scenarios. Therefore, we built a small number of task-specific “prompt-answer” pairs based on information science domain texts to fine-tune the model and improve its few-shot learning ability, thus making GPT3 more suitable for information science term extraction tasks.

Figure 1. GPT3-based term extraction process.

In order to make GPT3 implement the term extraction task, we designed a specification for term extraction in a text-generated manner (Figure 1.): in the inference phase, the input of the model is a sentence to be extracted, and the model is expected to output all the terms in the sentence and sort the them in the order of their occurrence. To achieve this goal, we need to construct “prompt-answer” pairs according to the above specification, where prompt is the sentence to be extracted, and answer is all the terms in the sentence. Then, the GPT3 model is fine-tuned so that it understands the task requirements and generates possible terms. In this way, the few-shot learning capability of the model can be improved with only a small amount of labeled data.

Experiments

In order to verify the performance of the proposed method, we compared three mainstream NLU models: BERT, SciBERT and RoBERTa. SciBERT was domain-adaptive pre-trained on large-scale scientific full-text, which is more suitable for scientific domain NLP tasks.

RoBERTa adopted a deeper training method, a more effective masking method, and a more comprehensive input representation.

Hyperparameter settings

The hyperparameters of each model are listed in Table 1. Since RoBERTa has a larger number of parameters compared to BERT, more epochs of fine-tuning were performed to obtain the best performance.

Table 1. Hyperparameters of each model.

<i>Model</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Max length</i>	<i>Batch size</i>	<i>Epoch</i>
BERT	bert-base-uncased	256	4	4
SciBERT	scibert-scivocab-uncased	256	4	4
RoBERTa	roberta-base	256	4	10
GPT3	davinci	auto	4	4

We divided the labeled text into training set and validation set according to the ratio of 9:1. For the GPT3, the datasets were processed into “prompt-answer” pairs format and uploaded to the OpenAI server for fine-tuning. For models such as BERT, the datasets were transformed into token format and fine-tuned on a local GPU-equipped server.

Analysis of experimental results

Based on the fine-tuned models to extract information science terms, the inference capabilities of each model are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Performance comparison of each model.

<i>Model</i>	<i>Precision</i>	<i>Recall</i>	<i>F1-score</i>
BERT	85.71%	86.60%	86.15%
SciBERT	86.15%	87.63%	86.88%
RoBERTa	77.45%	81.44%	79.40%
GPT3	93.00%	82.13%	87.23%

In the few-shot scenarios, the F1-score of GPT3 outperformed other models. This indicates that when there is a scarcity of labeled datasets, fine-tuning the GPT3 model based on few-shot learning can effectively guide the model to output the desired text content and format, thus reducing manual labeling labor and data costs to a certain extent. This result also shows that by constructing “prompt-answer” pairs fine-tuning model, it is possible to make the generative task-oriented model capable of information extraction.

For models such as BERT, although the amount of labeled data for specific tasks has been greatly reduced through fine-tuning, for cases where only a very small amount of labeled data exists, overfitting is likely to occur, which affects the inference capability of the model. Especially for models with more parameters such as RoBERTa, they are more vulnerable to the scale of data. Therefore, in order to make the BERT architecture model perform optimally, it is still necessary to construct a relatively large labeled dataset for fine-tuning.

However, the GPT3 still has flaws in its application. Models such as BERT can be trained, inferred and deployed at low cost due to their relatively small number of parameters. As the parameter size of the GPT3 is too large, researchers can only remotely operate the GPT3 models

- Language models are few-shot learners. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 33, 1877-1901.
- Ding, L., Zhang, Z., Liu, H., Li, J., & Yu, G. (2021). Automatic keyphrase extraction from scientific Chinese medical abstracts based on character-level sequence labeling. *Journal of Data and Information Science*, 6(3), 35-57.
- Li, P., Liu, Q., Cheng, Q., & Lu, W. (2021). Data set entity recognition based on distant supervision. *The Electronic Library*, 39(3), 435-449.
- Pinheiro, P., & Collobert, R. (2014). Recurrent convolutional neural networks for scene labeling. In *International conference on machine learning* (pp. 82-90). PMLR.
- Sager, J. C., Dungworth, D., & McDonald, P. F. (1980). *English special languages: principles and practice in science and technology*. Wiesbaden: Brandstetter.
- Si, Y., Wang, J., Xu, H., & Roberts, K. (2019). Enhancing clinical concept extraction with contextual embeddings. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*, 26(11), 1297-1304.
- Terryn, A. R., Hoste, V., & Lefever, E. (2022). Tagging terms in text: A supervised sequential labelling approach to automatic term extraction. *Terminology. International Journal of Theoretical and Applied Issues in Specialized Communication*, 28(1), 157-189.
- Yang, X., Bian, J., Hogan, W. R., & Wu, Y. (2020). Clinical concept extraction using transformers. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*, 27(12), 1935-1942.